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Causes of Extramarital Affairs: Lessons for Social Workers and Child Rights Advocates

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ABSTRACT: Seemingly, extramarital affair is occurring in all communities with substantial negative socio-economic and political consequences both on the couples, children and the neighborhoods; deserves urgent attention to address it. The rationale for the systematic literature review is to interrogate causes of the phenomenon, share knowledge to spark and inspire processes that will usher rapid growth from all directions. A systematic review of the literatures using information collected from different sources was actuated. Google search engine and others were used to search for articles. Only peer-reviewed articles published after 1999 were selected except extracts of fundamental mileage. However, articles published by staunch international organizations working in the area for years and produced indefatigable knowledge were stealthily appraised.

The study revealed that the causes are multifaceted and entail: cultural and traditional factors, strong desire for children, high level of education, loneliness, unattractive partner, lack of communication, poverty and financial hardships, lack of commitment to the marriage institution, dissatisfaction, access to the internet, lack of employment opportunities and working abroad, lack of personal boundaries, access to contraceptives, diseases and pandemics, substance abuse and drug addiction, domestic violence, lack of trust and respect, feeling unappreciated and care for, low level of education, normalization of infidelity, compulsive desire for sex, strong desire for revenge, stress at workplace, elevation in power, attachment style, childhood trauma, childhood exposure to infidelity, lack of moral standards and previous cheating, lack of religious commitment, low compatibility and empathy; and male dominance.

KEYWORDS: extramarital, sex, infidelity, causes, affairs

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is one of the most fundamental contracts a man and a woman can enter into despite their numerous differences including their world view (Barbara A. Atwood, 2011). Thus, commitment to the relationship to form a strong and healthy union, unified family and society is critical in any successful marriage (Atapour, Falsafinejad, Ahmadi, & Khodabakhshi-Koolae, 2021). Thus, it is a socially recognized and acceptable union, a legal contract between two unrelated individuals, usually a man and a woman that occurs in all human society (Odebo, James, Adegunju, & Julia, 2021).

Extramarital affairs the act of establishing and maintaining a sexual relationship outside a marriage with the anticipation of satisfying unmet needs which can be either physical, emotional or sexual has caused profound shock and dismay to many couples and their families (Stephen T. Fife, 2011). In modern societies, despite the huge changes in boundaries including emotional relationships, extramarital affairs is unacceptable in many civilized societies but still it is a widespread practice deafening by yelling for urgent social attention and action to eliminate it (Tsepalas, 2010). Seemingly, public attitudes towards marital infidelity is rapidly changing in some communities especially in the industrialized countries in which interestingly and increasingly, women, not men, are the first to stray from marriage, for example, in both the USA and the UK, 25% to 50% of the married women have at least one lover after they are married in any given marriage. Similarly, from 50% to 65% of the wedded men stray by the age of 40 (Adams, 2017). At present, 73% of the married people claimed to have had at least one affair. To reduce it with the ultimate objective of eliminating the behavior in the society by prohibition, death by stoning as prescribed by Islamic laws in the event of adultery (UIA, 2020).

Extramarital sex is one of the factors threatening family structure and consequently the most fundamental sense of belonging, performance, stability, endurance of marital relationship (Waweru, 2022). The types of infidelity include physical, emotional, cyber, object; and financial infidelity (Tristan McBain, 2022). Extramarital sexual relationship is common among all marriages in the United States of America with an estimate of 20% to 55% (Atkins, 2001), between 26% to 75% to be more significant (Eaves, 2007).

In the USA, one-third of all the divorces, at least one spouse has been involved in a marital infidelity behavior and as well, 34% of men and 19% of women in the adult groups in the USA have reported involvement in extramarital sexual relationships at one stage of their life (Messripour, Etemadi, Ahmadi, & Jazayeri, 2016). Even with the modest increment of 20% rate of extramarital affairs, one can safely suggest that it is prevalent and has eaten deep into the fabrics of marriages (Lişman & Holman, 2021). With the 20% to 25% of marital infidelity occurring in all marriages it is certain that it has multiple deleterious effects on the relationships and the married couples themselves, their immediate and even distant family members (Zapien, 2017).

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Marital infidelity, being a global problem, has caused tremendous effects on the society and has impacted differently different couples, socially, economically, psychologically, and culturally. Additionally, it is one of the most damaging behavior for the survival of marital relationship (Mapfumo, 2016). Most of the time if not all of the time, the damages inflicted by the discovery or revelation of marital infidelity can be very destructive not only to the marriage but to the entire family, the rebuilding of each can be time consuming and psychosocially expensive as it sometimes result in negative social, financial, medical, emotional, etc. impacts not mentioning separation, divorce, murder and suicides (Paul R. Amato, 2003). In addition to being the primary cause of divorce, spousal battering and other kind of domestic violence, it has no rival in disrupting marital relationship and worse of all, it is the third most difficult problem to resolve in marital problems and the fastest mean of spreading sexually transmitted infections including diseases such HIV/AIDS, therefore making it a great public health issue in some communities (Allen & Atkins, 2012).

METHODOLOGY

A systematic review of the literatures using information collected from different sources was actuated. Google search engine, google scholar, web of science, scopus database, etc. were used to search for these articles. During the search numeration combinations of words and phrases were used to ensure articles reflect the most recent knowledge and scholarly works. The systematic searches beget varied and voluminous articles which had to be sieved not only to meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria but to ensure the fundamental objectives of the study are wrangled.

Therefore, only peer-reviewed scholarly publications published after 1999 were selected except extracts perceived to be of basal mileage to the study. However, articles published by staunch international organizations known to have been working in the promotion of healthy and stable family for years and has produced indefatigable knowledge in the area and related issues were stealthily appraised.

Inclusion and Exclusion Procedures

The underneath procedures were adopted in articles inclusion. That is, only:

1. Peer-reviewed scholarly articles on extramarital affairs.
2. Peer-reviewed scholarly articles published from 1999 to 2024.
3. Articles on international or regional perspectives on extramarital affairs and related issues.
4. Articles on extramarital affairs and related issues published by international organizations with years of meritorious experiences in the promotion of healthy and stable family.

To exclude some articles from the review, the below captioned criteria were applied. That is:

1. Non-peer reviewed articles.
2. Articles published before 2000 unless critical and impactful.
3. Media generated articles including newspapers.
4. Articles not published in English language.

In spite of the fact that both qualitative and quantitative articles were trawled, only 202 articles out of 515 were qualified for the review which is largely due to a dearth of data. In essence, only peer-reviewed articles and publications by international organizations considered trustworthy because they occasioned standard, ethical; and robust studies were reviewed.

DISCUSSIONS

The literature review has revealed a wide range of issues pertaining to extramarital affairs. To discuss the causes, they are classified into various thematic issues consisting of: cultural and traditional factors, strong desire for children, high level of education, loneliness, unattractive partner, lack of communication, poverty and financial hardships, lack of commitment to the marriage institution, dissatisfaction, access to the internet, lack of employment opportunities and working abroad, lack of personal boundaries, access to contraceptives, diseases and pandemics, substance abuse and drug addiction, domestic violence, lack of trust and respect, feeling unappreciated and care for, low level of education, normalization of infidelity, compulsive desire for sex, strong desire for revenge, stress at workplace, elevation in power, attachment style, childhood trauma, childhood exposure to infidelity, lack of moral standards and previous cheating, lack of religious commitment, low compatibility and empathy; and male dominance. In essence, here are several factors that can be blamed for extramarital sexual activities and their wild spread in the communities (Jahan et al., 2017).

Cultural and traditional factors

Culture is claimed to be one of the most important inventions of the human race as it is not only a map for living but without it there is no society if not a needy one (Tadege, 2023). However, for a long time it has been wrongly applied to subject some segments of the society to abuse especially the vulnerable communities for instant, the women (Muna, 2020), children, the elderly persons, persons with disabilities, etc. and even critical social institutions such as the family and marriage (Adjei, 2018) concurring with: religiosity, cultural values, marital commitment and demographic factors have significantly influenced the involvement of married couples in extramarital affairs (Subchi, 2019). Extramarital sex can be influenced by geographical factors, cultural and ideological factors that include marrying from another religion and region generating incompatibility among couples (Odebode et al., 2021).

Strong desire for children

Power, wealth, prestige, etc. are one of the most sought things on the face of the modern earth making it more scarce daily and also one of the most fought for in the contemporary world (Juan, 2019). With these commodities, the owners command high socio-economic and political positions in some societies and becoming admired by all especially the impoverished and deprived communities (Cheng, 2013). In some societies, these can be acquired and measured via varying methods and means including the number of children (Hallsten, 2021) especially in agrarian societies thus, warranting some men dating different women irrespective of their marital status lending support to: in addition to commanding wealth, power and

prestige in the society, men are engage in marital infidelity both to meet their genes to produce the largest number of children and to meet their desire for sexual diversity urges with series of partners as they could not (Wróblewska-Skrzek, 2021). In some communities, infertile couples are socially, economically and politically stigmatized to the extent that they are denied leadership roles and positions and also membership in the ancestral world. To prove their fertility and restore their dignity, both males and females are circumstantially forced to be engaged in sex with multiple partners to prove their fertility. Thus, this desire to have biological children in a pronatalist society has not only resulted in extramarital relationship but unhealthy practices (Philip Teg-Nefaah Tabong, 2013).

High of level of education

Access to quality, affordable and relevant education is one of the fundamental human rights of all particularly the children (Right to Education Initiative, 2023) and (UNESCO, 2023). At any stage of educational career, the seekers and society expect some fundamental changes in their perspectives and approaches to issues including the ability to promptly, effectively and efficiently respond to situations and phenomenon (Andreea Orindaru, 2015). Because education accord people the power to question, rationalize and analysis issues objectively and scientifically, long held beliefs, tradition and practices have witnessed some fundamental shakes (Philip, 2011) including the marriage institution (Lawrence D. E. Ikamari, 2005) concurring with: persons with higher educational levels, stronger tendencies toward liberalization, non-Islamic beliefs were more tolerant toward extramarital sex, whereas gender and Christian beliefs had no significant influence (Liu, Lu, & Xie, 2021). Demographic variables, gender minority status, education, age, income, individual personality, prior infidelity experience, alcohol abuse, relationship dissatisfaction, religion, internet; and work mate association and context have been significantly cited as fundamental factors in marital infidelity practice in many communities around the globe (Fincham & May, 2017).

Loneliness

Most of the time if not all of the time, being surrounded by people and effectively interacting with them especially friends and acquaintances is fundamental in the psychosocial development of everyone regardless of the age (Berna, 2022). Additionally, interacting with people either physically or remotely widen one's social networks availing him or her some great opportunities for socio-economic and political developments (Hans-Georg Wolff, 2017). Similarly, residing in such atmospheric conditions accord one the environment required to think strategically to explore opportunities both nationally and internationally doing away with vilest thoughts and activities (Arenius, P., Clercq, 2005). However, living alone doesn't only deprived a person these development driven opportunities but also result to self-hate, committing antisocial behaviors, crimes and adopting rebellious attitudes toward even one's own family and close friends (Lasse Brandt, 2022) lending support to: lack of affection, being emotionally unavailable, feeling lonely or neglected by a partner, fear of intimacy, avoidance of conflict, seeking change or variety, falling out of love, commitment issues, resentment, self-esteem, body figure issues; and ego-boosting are hugely attributed to marital infidelity (Tristan McBain, 2022). Intimacy bankruptcy due to infidelity has resulted to some partners being literally forced to engaged in extramarital sexual activities, thus, in this situation loneliness is not only a salient product but also a fundamental cause of infidelity (Rokach & Philibert-lignières, 2015).

Unattractive partner

Decency and attractiveness are critical qualities that all rational persons would like to be known for and associated with. In this modern world with these overt qualities, one is easily like, love and even accorded rare opportunities (Marici M, Runcan R, Iosim I, 2023) including jobs, business opportunities, marriage offers in highly placed families and communities, exoneration from crimes and antisocial behaviors (Shihui Pan, 2021). Thus, the lack of these and other critical qualities like honesty doesn't only limit opportunities for prospect but worst of all, force some to be engage in activities that are detrimental to their health and personal development such skin bleaching, surgeries, etc. for beauty and also to sustain friends (Christopher A. D. Charles, 2011), social networks, social standing and even intimate partners (Adetoogun, 2023) concurring with: the lack of satisfaction and unattractiveness among others has significantly contributed to infidelity in some marital relationships (Atapour et al., 2021). Sexual frustration, sexual experience before marriage, sexual experience curiosity, unattractive partners, revenge on partners, marital discord, lack of attention boundaries, discrepancy in needs and goals, non-fulfillment of emotional needs, suppressed excitement, low esteem and negative self-image and sensational seeking are some of the common factors that usually lead to extramarital sex (Messripour et al., 2016). Different factors can be blamed for men being engaged in extramarital sexual relationship and can be broadly categorized into irritable wife, wife's body not being ideal, wife is menopause or sick, parents-in-laws interference, new sensation, loneliness because of distance, sex workers/girls friends being more communicative and romantic, getting a bonus, excessive sex libido, not being generally satisfied with the wife, effects of drug abuse and bad friends (Ainun Sajidah Evy Marlinda Agus Rachmadi, 2019).

Lack of communication

Communication being the bedrock of all institutions including society is one of the most important inventions of the human race (Evans Oluwagbamila Ayeni, 2019). With regular, effective and efficient communication, the required social bondage for togetherness, unity and solidarity is effortlessly built (Rod Troester, 1990). At any level of togetherness being at individuals, group and community levels, peace is fundamental and this is best established and sustained through understanding which cannot be attained without communication (Becker, 1982). Even the success and happiness in a marriage lies in effective communication (Aniekan L. Nyarks, 2023). Therefore, without regular, effective and efficient communication, not only large units of society are threaten but even basic social institutions such as the family and marriages as it results to the committing of antisocial behaviors and crimes (Julie Arnfred Bojesen, 2018) among others; lending support to: lack of regular communication, detachments and distant has significantly pushed military deployed spouses into marital infidelity (Alvarado, 2020). To prevent marital infidelity and its associated negative impacts such loneliness, emotional trauma, divorce, etc. it is critical that couples regularly and effectively communicate to uncover and address any underlying problems (Nasution & Sahri, 2020). Infidelity in most cases negatively affect the quality of couple relationship, resulting in difficulties in communication, sexuality; and violence which ultimately fuel extramarital sex and the risk of HIV/STI infection (Schensul et al., 2006).

Poverty and financial hardships

Seemingly, for anyone to live a productive life in the society, access to finance in addition to physical and mental fitness is nonnegotiable (Mai Huong Giang, 2019). However, poverty and its associated consequences are becoming common phenomena in the world particularly in developing societies. This can be associated to multiple of factors including poor governance, education system, conflicts, climate change, etc. (Servaas Van Der Berg, 2017). To survive during trial moments, people and communities have resorted to doing different things both legal, illegal (Luke Fleming, 2016), antisocial behaviors, etc. just to earn a living or sustain unreasonable life styles (Patrycja J. Piotrowska, 2014) concurring with: for women by engaging in extramarital sex they do not intend to have many children like some men but rather they want to gain more financial support to foot some critical bills for themselves and their offspring (Wróblewska-Skrzek, 2021). Some women are involved in extramarital affairs due to poverty, drug addiction, fear of being maltreated by pimps and furthermore being entrapped in the ugly trade/activities. Economic and financial hardships have contributed to some couples engagement in extramarital relationships to foot compelling bills (Atapour et al., 2021). Lack of strong beliefs, economic difficulties, socio-cultural factors; and high societal level of acceptance of the practice have significantly contributed to extramarital sex in some communities (Virginia Wanjiru, Niceta Ileri, 2020). Men becoming breadwinners' increases their chances of involving in marital infidelity while in the case of women becoming breadwinner decreases the chance, however, for both men and women, economic dependency is associated with a higher likelihood of engaging in infidelity especially when it comes to the men compare to the women (Munsch, 2015). Some women in trying to be financially independent by taking some loans from individuals and financial institution have caused them to be engaged in marital sex just to settle some of these debts especially when they are not being supported by their husbands (Mtenga, Pfeiffer, Tanner, Geubbels, & Merten, 2018). Financial meltdowns resulting in significant economic losses, closure of work sites and/or limited operation, unemployment, etc. has precipitated marital infidelity in some communities and groups (Rokach & Chan, 2023). For some women, striving to ensure financial independence, obligations to repay loans taken from financial institutions with limited or no support from their husbands has forced them to be engaged in extramarital affairs (Mtenga et al., 2018).

Lack of commitment to the marriage institution

For any undertaken regardless of being, social, economic or political to pay dividend, high level of commitment and efficacy is required (Hassan Ballou, 2009). With commitment, the required time, physical, mental, psychological and financial resources are convincingly allocated for the attainment of the set goals (Beatrice van der Heijden, 2022). However, without commitment and the required support, partners become demotivated which sometime does not only result in disengagement but the engagement in fraudulent activities jeopardizing the whole undertaken including marriage (John Garin Isaac Ameyaw, 2023) reaffirming: one of the strongest motivation factors for spouse to be engage in extramarital sexual relations was as a result of partners not investing adequate resources and time in the marriage (Stinley, 2017).

Dissatisfaction

Man as a rational human being hardly s/he does or venture into anything especially the legal ones without a purpose. Generally, the purpose of his or her actions is meant to satisfy a need either at individual or community level. In the event that identified needs cannot be satisfied, it is almost certain that s/he will instantly abandon it or will never pay for it if it is a product on sale (Stephen Thielke, 2011). In the case of joint engagements or unions s/he withdraws his or her participation and commences searching for partners constituting infidelity in the case of marriage (Scott, Rhoades, Stanley, Allen, & Markman, 2013), affirming: lack of sexual satisfaction as a key factor in individuals' sexual health and overall well-being has largely been associated with extramarital relationship (María del Mar Sánchez-Fuentes, Pablo Santos-Iglesias, Juan Carlos Sierraa, 2013). Interpersonal factors, marital conflicts and lack of sexual satisfaction are key factors frequently associated with extramarital relationships (Messripour et al., 2016). Marital dissatisfaction and disruption does not only weaken the quality of marriage but also leads to extramarital sexual relationship (DeMaris, 2013). Some men are involved in extramarital sex because they lack that needed company from their wives which ultimately leads to dissatisfaction and anger (Charlotte McDonald, 2014). Marital infidelity can be caused by many factors however; dissatisfaction with a partner or the relationship is a fundamental reason and deserves to be given serious consideration in mending infidelity and its negative outcomes (Scheeren, Martínez de Apellániz, & Wagner, 2018). Majority of married men who hire the services of prostitutes are unhappy in their marriages (Monto & McRee, 2005). In Zimbabwe, men are mostly engaged in concurrent sexual partnership due to dissatisfaction with their wives as there were many reports in which men are not involved in extramarital sexual relationship because of being satisfied with their wives treatments and sexual relationships (Mugweni, Pearson, & Omar, 2015). Men like women believe sex is an integral part of marriage and any dissatisfaction can result in extramarital sex especially by the men who seem to be more sexually active than their wives/counterparts (Sinikka, 2008). Men who are engaged in infidelity/extramarital relationship reported being more relaxed and satisfied with prostitutes compare to their own wives (Charlotte McDonald, 2014). Low quality of relationship couple with conflict and sexual dissatisfaction were reported as one of the main factors that encourage both men and women to be involved in extramarital sexual relationship (Mtenga et al., 2018).

Access to the internet

Science and technology has long since been indispensable but today it is more apparent than ever because of several factors for example, quick and instant access to information or data for immediate and smart decision making, quick access to goods and services, national and international security/safety, borderless access to education, healthcare, executing national and international business transactions, mobilization of financial and human resources, just to name a few (Donna L, 2004). To cost effectively act on these needs, more especially access to educational materials the internet has played a critical role as sometimes it only requires the click on a button (Kwaku Darko Amponsah, 2022). However, in addition to its inherent disadvantages, its calculated abuse has significantly threaten the survival of many institutions including the basic ones such as intimate relationships, marriages and the family (Liu J, Yu NN, Cheng M, 2023) as substantiated by: marital infidelity is increasing especially among married men fundamentally due to freedom and the use of technology among women (Wen, 2019). Spousal violence and lack of effective communication has resulted to a significant increment in the committing of marital infidelity especially by young women who have resorted to online dating (Atapour et al., 2021). The internet due to practices like social distancing and other opportunities offers by it, it has become common place for dating that subsequently lead to the increase in extramarital affairs especially during the COVID-19 and immediately after it (Rokach &

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Chan, 2023). Married couples turning to the social networking websites/internet for infidelity activities is not only a clear indication of marital dissatisfaction but the comfort and anonymity in searching and engaging partners for extramarital affairs(Adams, 2017). People with mental and emotional illness reported high levels of social networking services/internet infidelity than those without and they have the greatest challenges in guarding their relationship against infidelity(Abbasi, 2022). With the advent and proliferation of accessible and affordable internet services, infidelity has not only moved to another level, but has been made easy with the numerous chatrooms, personal websites/homepages, pornographic websites, etc. as it cost nearly nothing to book a street girl other than the initial computer, smartphone and internet service or the fee at an internet café (Bimbi, 2007). To some extent, demographic factors, personality traits, and access to sexual information like pornographic materials especially in the internet has significant impact on the spousal commitment of marital infidelity(Haseli, Shariati, Nazari, Keramat, & Emamian, 2019).

Lack of employment opportunities and working abroad

With the unprecedented rise of unemployment and underemployment both nationally, regionally and internationally it did not only forced governments to rapidly innovate strategies to curb it but it has equally compelled individuals to be frantically engaged in searching for jobs both locally and globally in numerous ways. In the search for employment internal and external migration both legally and illegally is not uncommon (Yahya Muhammed Bah, 2023). In the case of external migration especially the illegal one it has resulted to people being near-permanently separated from their families since they cannot travel back to their countries of origin due to lack of authentic documents(Mbaye, 2014). In accordance with the length of stay away especially from legitimate intimate partners, some have resorted to some kind of criminal and antisocial behaviors including extramarital affairs to meet some biological needs(Mah Yong Xin, 2020) concurring with: in Indonesia sex is only legal with married couples however, married men whose wife work as migrant workers abroad have been involved in seeking sex outside to satisfy their sexual needs(Rifai, Afandi, & Saputra, 2019). In Cambodia, in addition to women culturally supporting and believing in men should be engaged in marital infidelity, male dominance in sex and personal relationships; and work related mobility, the practice is sharply on the increase(Thapa, Yang, & Chan, 2020). Similarly, when the ratios of employment between men and women are equal, extramarital relationship rarely takes place(Rob Stephenson, 2010). In addition to the rapid economic growth Ghana is witnessing, the confinement of sex between classes (i.e. low class and the low, the upper class and the class) and the strong desire for some to come out of such marriages plus the rural-urban migration for employment opportunities have resulted to the rise of extramarital sex in urban China (Zhang, Wang, & Pan, 2021).

Lack of personal boundaries

Human beings like physical objects or a piece of land has boundaries that must be promoted, observed and respected for independence and control over their bodies. Therefore, technically and legally people's bodies belong to them and to no one else even if it is regarded a gift from God/Allah(Aramesh K., 2009). However, some people because of lack of strict control over their bodies they have nearly become a common property warranting some abuses(Silvia StrakaLyse, Montminy, 2008) including complete domination, improper touching, etc. which subsequently open the doors for dating, intimate relationship and engagement in extramarital affairs in case of those who are married(Lammers, Stoker, Jordan, Pollmann, & Stapel, 2011) substantiating: extramarital relationship like most social problems has some developmental stages such as formation, engagement, and adjustments which are critical in preventing, minimizing the impacts and addressing it reaffirming the scholarly findings that personality trait like extro-version and narcissism are important factors in the causes of extramarital sex(Atapour et al., 2021). Men who displayed high level of social deviant personality traits, heightened sensation-seeking, impulsivity, sexual risk taking; and criminality tend to express a penchant short-term mating including extramarital sex (Davis, Vaillancourt, & Arnocky, 2020).

Access to contraceptives

To further avert overpopulation and spare women from the associated illnesses from frequent and unplanned deliveries or births, family planning through the use safe practices including the usage of contraceptives have become legitimate and common practices in most societies(Mehreen Mookerjee, 2023). Although it is not without limitations and unintended consequences, its abuse has accorded unfaithful partners leverage to be engage in cheating including extramarital affairs(Marcia Lynn Whicker, 1986) reaffirming: the knowledge and ability to use condoms accurately to prevent HIV/AIDS, STI, and other diseases has motivated some partners to engage in extramarital sexual activities (Putra, 2019). In addition to the undesirable contraception side effects for example diminished vaginal lubrication contributing to sexual pleasure disruption, some men denounced the women's use of contraceptives because it result in infidelity(Nkonde H, Mukanga B, 2023). In many developing societies Islamic and Roman Catholic leaders strongly disapproved the use of contraceptives associating it with moral degradation, indiscriminate sexual behaviors, early sexual debut, and the freedom to illicit extramarital sex(J.C Konje, 1999).

Diseases and pandemics

Of recent, the world has started witnessing diseases and pandemics that are complex, very contagious and seriously threatening life and living with no treatment of any sort(Nita Madhav, Ben Oppenheim, Mark Gallivan, Prime Mulembakani, Edward Rubin, 2018). With such types of pandemics, people don't only died, become persons with disabilities but vast majority of the population is highly restricted in terms of interaction, movement and engagement in outdoors economic activities to control the spread and impacts while deepening poverty, criminal activities and antisocial behaviors(Anagnostou, Michella; Moreto, William D.b; Gardner, Charlie J.c; Doberstein, 2021). In some instances some people including the married ones, have had sexual intercourse with the minors and multiple of adults to treat some diseases including HIV/AIDS (Banwari Meel, 2003)concurring with: the increment in financial, social and emotional stress brought in to some families by pandemics such as COVID-19 has significantly contributed to some couples being involved in extramarital sexual relationships(Erica A. Michell, 2023). The stress associated with pandemic such as COVID-19 has significantly increased people involvement marital infidelity as it has lowered relational and sexual satisfaction(Rokach & Chan, 2023).

Substance abuse and drug addiction

For years, man has been in serious combats with different issues to ensure he survive in this planet and even the others he is intensely exploring. However, this is not without notorious challenges being in the form of wild animals, diseases, natural disaster, etc.(Topluoglu Seher, Taylan-Ozkan, Aysegul Taylan-Ozkan Aysegul, 2023) and (Abhaya S Prasad, Louis Hugo Francescutti, 2017). To address these challenges, he has made

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several attempts to find both temporal and permanent solutions including the manufacturing of drugs for the treatment of different ailments. Drugs and related substances though meant to cure diseases and ailments in the societies is creating lot of socio-economic, political and health havoc especially when abused by the youthful population and responsible adults (UNDCP, 1995) and (United Nations, 2023) substantiating: in some Iranian communities marital infidelity causes can be catalogued into partners' emotional issues, cultural and social factors, substance abuse, partners' psychological issues, financial difficulties; and unmet sexual needs (Atapour et al., 2021). Marital infidelity is associated with heavy alcohol use among cohabiters and spouses and depressive symptoms among spouses (Wenger & Frisco, 2021) and also one of the many kinds of marital infidelity affairs revolves around sexual addiction and the inability to say simple and plain "NO" (Robert Huizenga, n.d.). In India, men being engaged in extramarital sex is mostly attributable to numerous factors that include husband's and wife's age, wife's perception of domestic violence, husband's education and place of birth, husband's alcohol consumption, wife's unwillingness to engage in marital sex; and the types of marital sexual acts (Schensul et al., 2006).

Domestic violence

For any progress and development to be registered in any community or group as small as two persons, peace is a critical put (Anna-Karin Evaldsson, 2005). Thus, if peace is to be established and sustained in a society, peaceful habitation between marriage partners constituting the commencement of a family the foundation of society is fundamental and cannot be compromised (Sunday David Edinyang, 2012). In spite of this central position of the family and marriage globally, there have been unprecedented rise in domestic violence (WHO, 2024). With the prevalence of intimate violence, the matrimonial homes become a hot chair for some members threatening the love and caring for each other as married partners. For a peaceful mind; some partners had resorted to dating outside their marriage especially when divorce is near impossible due to multiple of factors (Mark Mohan Kaggwa, 2021) concurring with: the conservative attitudes of husbands beating their wives and also being the sole decision maker in the family has significantly contributed to the rise of extramarital sex risky behaviors in three African countries (Rob Stephenson, 2010). Domestic violence which can take different forms has significantly affected the intimacy between couples as the experience of physical or non-physical abuse has a negative association with psychosexual and sexual functioning in both women and men which ultimately leads to some immoral behaviors (Sierra JC, Arcos-Romero AI, Álvarez-Muelas A, 2021).

While the rate of sexual distress discovered to be considerably higher in ladies who were exposed to sexual abuse during pregnancy, interestingly no significant difference was revealed between sexual abuse and female sexual dysfunction however, sexual abuse during pregnancy was identified to be a risk factor for sexual distress which is a critical factor in extramarital relationship (Hacer Alan Dikmen, 2020).

Lack of trust and respect

Strong union is fundamental in the success of any institution being social or political in nature. To ensure the establishment of solid union at any social strata and its continuity the promotion and protection of the fundamental rights including trust, respect, equality, etc. cannot be brushed aside (Mohammed Saaida, 2024). Thus, in unions like marriage, brushing aside trust, respect and equality is a huge threat to the union (Abdulgaffar O. Arikewuyo, 2020) as it leads others to commence phone snooping, searching for partners whom they can trust, share their hearts with and deal with them with care and respect. In marriage being customary or legal lack of confidence can lead to infidelity (Rokach & Chan, 2023) lending support to: romantic relationships especially marriage is hugely anchored on trust and confidence in which financial infidelity consisting of hiding expenditures, savings, debts; and incomes have threaten relationships warranting some partners to be engaged in extramarital affairs to anger partners anticipating a change in behavior (Garbinsky, Gladstone, Nikolova, & Olson, 2020). Because he humiliated me and blamed me to the point that I could not stand him anymore, I had to make friends to escape such situation and worst of all there was no trust and I became more helpless to get out of all these miseries with an alternate (A Study of the Processes and Contextual Factors of Marital Infidelity; Neda Atapou 2021).

Trust may be the single most important ingredient for the development and maintenance of happy, well-functioning relationship, its development in romantic relationship as an approach to stability and avoidance of problems is a direct conclusion that any iota of distrust doesn't only lead to antisocial acts including extramarital affairs but divorce (Abdulgaffar O. Arikewuyo, 2020).

Feeling unappreciated and care for

For any shared commitment to be successfully accomplished, the team members must feel being valued and appreciated as it is one of cardinal indicators of being regarded as a great team player even if one is not a game changer (Robbins, 2019). In unions such as intimate relationship and/or marriage which demand absolute devotion, caring and sharing even one's own hearts and feelings, being valued and appreciated is one of the bedrocks (Jill Iroz Webb, 2020). In the absence of appreciation and love in contracts like marriage, the heart and love will undoubtedly vanish in search of a third party culminating to extramarital affairs (Jahan et al., 2017) as substantiated: the factors associated with marital infidelity can be broadly clubbed into personal, relationship, third-party; and situational factors (Varma, 2023). Men who are engaged infidelity/extramarital relationship reported being more relaxed, comfortable and valued with prostitutes compare to their own wives (Charlotte McDonald, 2014). Sometimes husbands' unreasonable treatment of their wives like lack of care and attention, nonchalant behaviors, lack of emotional support and love has forced some women to be involved in extramarital affairs (Aminat Adeola Odebode, 2022). Lack of appreciation and spending less time in activities as spouse reportedly contributes to extramarital relationships (Alfred DeMaris, 2012).

Low level of education

Education which seemingly occupies the driving seat of any individual and collective development is not a mere social service in a nation. Education as a critical input for people being able to rationalize things and quickly make objective decisions cannot be undervalued in the manner in which people response to issues to judicious unify society by avoiding immoral and illegal behaviors. Thus, it goes without emphasis, that there is a strong correlation between people's level of education, awareness and engagement in antisocial behaviors including extramarital affairs (Jahan et al., 2017) as they are intellectually well-grounded and equipped to weight the pros and cons of their behaviors (Maureen Ogwokhademhe, 2013): in a community where the ratios to men and women are equal and the majority of the populace has attained at least primary education, it is less likely for extramarital sex to occur as found in five African countries (Rob Stephenson, 2010). In Sub-Sahara Africa, transactional sex including

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infidelity is commonly practiced by men with less education and less income compared to those with higher education and those with no permanent source of income (Jewkes, Morrell, Sikweyiya, Dunkle, & Penn-Kekana, 2012). In Lagos, gender, age, religious affiliation and level of educational attainment significantly influence the practice of extramarital affairs among married adults (Maureen Ogwohademhe, 2013).

Normalization of infidelity

Coexistence of any kind and at any level must be underpinned by strong standard rules of engagement that clearly articulate what is acceptable and unacceptable. While the acceptable behaviors and practices are classified normal, the unacceptable ones are clubbed as abnormal and punishable (Maryam Serat, 2022). However, because of societal transformation and desire for development, overtime some unacceptable behaviors and practices become acceptable attracting no punishment of any kind. Therefore, the practice of any abnormal behavior without any form of punishment, result to its normalization and sometime overt practice with no iota of shame (Blake .E. Ashforth, 1977). Spousal and public perception toward marital infidelity significantly influences it happening in the communities since it does not anymore cause some emotional and psychological worries that result in negative mental health and physical discomfort (Shrout & Weigel, 2018). The people who are permissive with respect to premarital sex or coitus and those regard extramarital sexual activities as acceptable, disassociate sex, love and marriage are more at risk of being engaged in extramarital sex (Weis & Slosnerick, 1981). In Cambodia, the liberal attitudes toward extramarital sex has played a significant part in the increase of HIV/AIDS spread among spouses (Thapa, Yang, & Nget, 2019). Extramarital infidelity does not only expose Cambodian women to HIV infection but its practice is on the increase due to the country's double standards and the fact that it is often socially and culturally condoned (Thapa et al., 2020). The occurrence of marital infidelity in the community is linked with individual personality, interpersonally factors, contextual predictors, outcomes and reactions, beliefs and attitudes, prevalence, conceptualization and in addition sometimes it is also associated with internalization, sexism, racism, heterosexism, cissexism, classism, etc. (Weiser, 2022).

Compulsive desire for sex

To survive man is created with needs that must to be met in the most appropriate and judicious manner to avert conflict, insecurity and even lawlessness in the society (Lewis J., 2017) and (United States Institute of Peace, 2018). Some of these needs can be classified as basic while others are luxurious in nature and character. Irrespective of the classification, when not met can sometime create problems for some individuals especially those with inadequate problem management and resolution capacities/skills resulting to all-out search for it despite the possibilities of violating some laws, moral and ethics (Anne Abaho, 2020). The desire for sex as a biological need is no exception leading to extramarital affairs in the case of the married ones (Somaye Robatm, 2024) and (Rokach & Chan, 2023) as substantiated: extramarital sex is linked to several factors such as personal values, sexual opportunities, stronger sexual interest, more permissive values, lower subjective satisfaction with the marriage union, weaker network ties to partner; and quality of the marital relationship defeating sexual exclusivity (Treas & Giesen, 2000). Different studies have cited different factors motivating married couples to be engaged in extramarital sex which include compulsive need for sex, insatiable need for sexual pleasure, the fear of close intimacy, the soothing of the men's psyche as the prostitute is not demanding any emotional attachment in such temporal relationship, to shame and humiliate women in satisfying their hatred for women/misogyny (Schwartz's Weblog, 2011). Men who are sexually liberal, think much about extramarital sex, masturbate and participate in other areas of the sex industry are more likely to be involved in extramarital sex (Monto & McRee, 2005).

Strong desire for revenge

To live together harmoniously, respect and patient with each other is critical. Respect in its broader terms including promoting and observing the societal ethics, culture, legislations, moral standards, etc. all meant to control and properly direct people behaviors and energy for the betterment of society through peaceful coexistence (Yumarma, 2011). To achieve this, communities and institutions have established enforcement and disciplinary agencies. Thus, it is critical conflicts prevention; resolution strategies and plans are centralized, adequately discussed and expeditiously executed or implemented to avert people taking the laws and ethics into their own hands with the view to revenge while unconsciously increasing crimes and antisocial behaviors in the communities (Amegashie, 2008) and even in noble institution like the marriage and family (Frank D. Day, 1963) concurring with: dark triad traits mostly consisting of narcissism, Machiavellianism and psychopathy qualities often characterized by manipulation, emotional coldness, lack of empathy, deception, dishonesty, etc. strongly demonstrate and predict women's own infidelity, their perceived vulnerability to a partner's infidelity and revenge in response to extramarital sex (Gayle Brewer, 2015). Revenge has contributed to the spread of marital infidelity as it provides additional positive emotional benefits as the victims feel good about gaining a sense of power and control, feeling pride about oneself at being on the side of some spiritual primal justice as s/he keeps imagining how the target is suffering (Morrisette, 2012). Majority of the participants who felt they are victims of partners' transgression exhibited revenge reaction which is more emotional than rational and hardly have they yielded the anticipated consequences or success, this type of reaction is psychopathic being the best predictor for revenge thoughts and actions (Clemente, 2021). The findings identified the following eight key motivating factors that contribute to marital infidelity: anger or revenge, falling out of love, situational factors and opportunities, commitment issues, unmet needs, sexual desire, wanting variety; and low self-esteem (Timothy J Legg, 2019). In some instances, extramarital sex is a product of partners not being able to adequately resolve traumatic events and also foster permanent forgiveness in marriage (de Stefano & Oala, 2008).

Stress at workplace

To be healthy and remain so for a reasonable period of time requires among other things to be psychological fit. Thus, the psyche of a human being is fundamental in his or her effective and efficient functioning for his or her personal and societal development (Mark Bates, 2010). To attain this critical goal, individual and society must do all within their purview to prevent, eliminate if not minimize the negative impacts of any stressful activity (Tina Bui, 2021) including those in workplaces as they can have similar or more negative impacts on workers' effective execution of other functions outside the work environment including attending to communal, family and partners social and biological needs (Qiqi Chen, 2022) lending supports to: patients with sexual dysfunctions reporting marital infidelity suffer relational problems with the primary couple, high stress at work, longer secondary/primary relationship span, higher risk of conflicts within the primal couple and the family (Fisher et al., 2009). Elevated job stress especially among the dual-earner couples significantly negative affect marital relationship leading to decrease marital satisfaction a

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recipe for extramarital affairs (Putri, 2016). Higher workload of a partner can prove deleterious for effective marital relationship functioning and if not properly managed can result in serious spillover and crossover from dissatisfaction to immoral behaviors including extramarital sexual relationship among other marital problems (Justin A. Lavner, 2017). Women who practice infidelity associated behaviors on social networks indicates less sexual satisfaction, less emotional intimacy, less relationship satisfaction; and greater ambivalence due to stressful working conditions (González-Rivera, Aquino-Serrano, & Pérez-Torres, 2020).

Elevation in power

We go to work for a number of reasons that include the desire to be part of the national development processes as responsible citizens. We also go to work to be economically independent in order to take care of our needs particularly the basic ones without asking for support from anyone (Bradley L. Hardy, 2016). In whatever kind of work we are engaged, we want to see some progress in our life and living conditions. This is attainable through different means such as promotion in conventional setting or making more profits in business (Fodio Garba, 2021). Interestingly, in whichever way, we are elevated with some reasonable power which if not appropriately applied can resort to being engaged in criminal and antisocial behaviors including cheating on one's partner (Dew, Saxey, & Mettmann, 2022) concurring with: The elevation of power through whatever means if not properly managed, has the potential to lead some people to start behaving abnormally including the engagement in extramarital sexual relationship because they both force or simply attract partners, interestingly this applies to both men and women (Lammers et al., 2011). Taken together there is a correlation between the level of education and occupation vis-à-vis the financial power among others they come with and the practice of infidelity (Ian Smith, 2012).

Attachment style

Seemingly, the meaning of life and living lies with the interaction of people near and far as it demonstrates a degree of being accepted and valued first in the family and community (Nyoman Arya Maha Putra, b & Sri Yonaa, 2019). With acceptance and constant interaction, the opportunities for development and progress are opened. It is natural that as we interact some kind of social bonds or attachments are established first starting with our family members including our parents. Thus, the ability to establish and maintain strong social bonds especially at the family level are critical in life since generally, the fulfillment of certain desires depends on the degree of the bond (Zahide Tepeli Temiz, 2018), the stronger they are, the more we are likely to be comfortable and the weaker they are, the more it is likely that we will be dissatisfied which ultimately affects our future union with others including our intimate partners (Mohammadi K, Samavi A, 2016) culminating to some criminal and antisocial behaviors: extramarital affair like most marital problems is a well-rooted source of conflict that is likely to increase children's risky behaviors, that results to poor attachment styles, bad future relationships; and generational patterns of conflicts (Borst, 2015). Spouses whose partners suffer from either high or low attachment are more likely to perpetuate marital infidelity (Ghiasi, 2021). The nature of attachment style and subsequent working models developed in childhood impact later adult relationships, especially romantic one (Bennett et al., n.d.). High attachment avoidance that encompasses being fearful and dismissive has been identified as a factor for marital infidelity but there are some variations for example, while it is a high risk factor among black African American it is not the case among European in American and Latinos in America (Parker & Campbell, 2017). Men with insecure attachment compared to those with secure attachment are more prone to marital infidelity as they are mostly poor in conflict management (Bogda, 2012). Spouses with greater anxiety and avoidance attachment style are more associated with stronger desire for marital infidelity so too it is with spouses with greater dismissive and fearful attachment style (Ghiasi, 2021). Avoidant attached spouses have a high tendency of distancing themselves from their partners or developing a pervasive conflict pattern that leads to loneliness, psychological, physical morbidity and idealization of partner (Pereira, 2013). There is a significant correlation between extramarital sex and different attachment styles for example, ambivalent attachment style, avoidant attachment style, safe style, positive perfectionism and negative perfectionism (Maryam, 2021). There are so many factors that can be blamed for marital infidelity and they include depression, anxiety, PTSD in some cases, decreased self-esteem, attachment issues; and more (Sly, 2021). The data analyzing indicated that the attachment style of those who had infidelity in their marital infidelity in their marital life was avoiding attachment style (Hatamy, Fathi, Gorji, & Esmaeily, 2011). Anxiously attached, married people are potentially at risk for infidelity, either on their part or on the part of their spouses thus, attachment style can possibly predict which romantic partners remain faithful to each other (Rokach & Philibert-lignières, 2015).

Childhood trauma

Theologically, life and living is not only for a test but it is naturally full of ups and downs. Thus, the capacity to be able to prevent, eliminate or minimize the negative impacts of the mishaps especially at tender age is critical in living a meaningful life in the future (Elizabeth Crouch, 2019). However, there are certain mishaps in life; their impacts are too disastrous for individuals and communities to effectively handle without the interventions of professionals. In the event that they are not amicably resolved or poorly resolved, they don't only harm the victims physically but also affect their ability to coexist with others (Öğr Üyesi, 2022) including intimate partners without being involved in antisocial behaviors such as cheating and groundless allegations (Michael Fitzgerald & Hamstra, 2021): traumatic events have statistical negative impacts on romantic relationship warranting uncalled behaviors including extra-dyadic (Polser, 2020). Cumulatively, childhood trauma can lead to some severe interpersonal problems including couple dissatisfaction, one of the main causes of infidelity (Gobout, Morissette Harvey, Cyr, & Bélanger, 2020). People hooked on marital infidelity had serious emotional and psychological damages/trauma in their childhood including deprivation, helplessness, emotional breakdown, intergenerational divide, centralized parenting, etc. which have ultimately negatively affected every aspect of their adulthood including their education, occupation, economy and their involvement in extramarital relationships (Azizpour & Mirsaleh, 2021). Persons who engage in marital infidelity must have suffered from different traumas at childhood which entail behavioral and physical traumas such as abuse, punishment, parental aggression, force and coercion; incorrect parenting (e.g. extreme affection, parental self-centeredness, lack of supervision, and behavioral contradiction); and malfunctioning family structure (e.g. family conflict, border tension and inequality between children) (Safia, 2022). Childhood emotional abuse is strongly connected with difficulties in empathetic accuracy and that empathetic inaccuracy in part mediates the association between childhood emotional abuse and adult dissatisfaction resulting in marital infidelity among other malbehaviors (Maneta, 2015). Respondents displaying relatively high levels of childhood trauma tend to report insecure attachment consisting of

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fear, preoccupation and dismissing attachment styles that often leads to negative physical, emotional, relational mental effects (Pillai, 2022). Childhood trauma is significantly correlated with the adulthood types of attachment and involvement in marital infidelity (Yumbul, Cavusoglu, & Geyimcia, 2010). Participants felt that by witnessing the miserable situations they found their parents in as a result of marital infidelity is highly likely to affect them and their marital relationship at adulthood (Siguan, Ong, & Canete, 2021). People with schemas including abandonment, instability, mistrust, abuse, emotional deprivation, defectiveness/shame, rejection and disconnection; and social isolation/alienation schemas, often have difficulties in childhood as they tend to seek refuge from one relationship to another (Karimi et al., 2023).

Childhood exposure to infidelity

At birth, children are like plain sheet of paper, so their value is basically anchored on what is written on them (Halley Bachelor, 2014). Thus, children like any other human being are born with nothing which includes character and behaviors. All what they are at the moment and are likely to be in the future is learned in society including the family and peers. There are different ways children learn chiefly through the socializing agencies such as the family, schools, media, peers, etc. Some learning can be through the conventional methods while others through unconventional ones. Thus, it is principally through interaction and exposure that children learn (Uchenna Ajake, 2010). In this regard, exposing children to bad behaviors including extramarital sex affairs overtly tantamount to not only teaching them the behavior but worst of all approving and normalizing it for future practice (Kamini Tanwar, 2016) concurring with: childhood trauma due to exposure to abuse including witnessing parental infidelity has resulted in adulthood hardship especially in maintaining healthy, trust worthy and fruitful marital relationship (Fulu et al., 2017). The participants whose parents engaged in extramarital sexual relationship were more likely to have engaged in extradyadic behaviors themselves (Marie Paredes, 2010). The findings indicate significant relationship between parents' extramarital affairs and respondents own participation in extramarital sexual relationship at adulthood (Alexandra E. Schmidt, Mary S. Green, 2016).

Lack of moral standards and previous cheating

For society to exist through coexistence, the national legislations and international conventions alone may not suffice as the enforcement agencies cannot be everywhere at all time. Above all, nations may not be able to fund that judiciary system to judiciously, effectively and efficiently adjudicate all cases which may ultimately result to a chaotic society the disadvantaged bearing the main burden (Frank Emmert, 2019). Thus, to prevent, eliminate and/or minimize conflicts including antisocial behaviors in the society, it is a must that the conventional legal system and non-conventional ones work harmoniously (Boyane Tshela, 2016). For instant, simple act like isolation, naming and shaming, etc. at the family, peer group, village level, etc. can significantly deter people from committing or recommitting certain abnormal behaviors including extramarital sex because that can be enough psychologically torture (Faradj Koliev, 2018) not mentioning the capability of criminalization and strong enforcement of the legislations lending support to: the propensity toward extramarital infidelity is attributable to lack of adherence to moral standards and past unfaithful conducts (Lişman & Holman, 2021). Individuals in committed relationship were more upset or distressed by their partner's infidelity, especially sexual infidelity, compared to those not in one (Kato & Okubo, 2023). In addition to being unhappy with current relationship, women engage in infidelity to switch to long-term mates for sexual relationship is not impossible in a moral decaying communities (Brand, Markey, Mills, & Hodges, 2007). The assumption that parents' infidelity does not harm children is untrue, runs contrary to public policy, and it frustrates the efforts to save them through court actions (Wardle, 2003).

Lack of religious commitment

All human being seemingly believe that the earth and everything on it including humanity did not come by accident, thus, they must be created and sustained by something that is more powerful than everything on it. To express gratitude, be attached to the creator, ask for more support and protection, man started offering prayers in different ways and at different time of the day and night laying the foundation for different religions (Matt Bradshaw, 2018). However, during most of the early days, people have named and worship different things including their own creation as their gods. This practice was gradually eradicated with the coming of religions such as Christianity and Islam one of the biggest religions on the face of the earth (Joan-Pau Rubiés, 2006). These great religions came with not only the way how to worship one God but how people should conduct themselves to peacefully coexist by approving and condemning certain practices no matter how long they have been in practice. Thus, religion became a way of life with categorically stated "do and don'ts" in which some criminal and antisocial behaviors are condemned with hell fire after death (Philip K. Hitti, 1970). With sincere commitment to the various teachings, the faithful ones don't only fight against evil and immoral practices but completely desisted from it including extramarital affairs (Mansoureh Ebrahimi, 2017) concurring with: apart from the absence of internal adherence, lack of religion has become a major contributor to the prevalence of extramarital relationships in some communities (Atapour et al., 2021). The negative effects of extramarital affairs are strongly linked with lack of religious commitments and wives/women being out of the labour force (DeMaris, 2013). The discrepancy in the definition and understanding of marital infidelity due to multiple factors such as gender, sexual orientation, frequency of attending religious services, knowledge of the practice in one's family of origin, level of education; and personal experiences does not only promote its occurrence in some communities but it also leads to some difficulties in preventing it and supporting victims (Schonian, 2013).

Low compatibility and empathy

To accelerate developments in the globe, partnership has become indispensable (Anne Vestergaard, 2021). This partnership can be at international, regional, national and individual level. Partnership like all unions is underpinned by certain principles and philosophies including compatibility and having common goals. These are fundamental because they keep the partnership ticking and focus while building strong social bonds among players (Mingze Li, 2022). With strong social bonds, compatibility, sympathy and empathy is boosted and heightened resulting in unflinching support to each as no one would be willing to hurt others feelings by engaging in criminal and antisocial behaviors including cheating (Stupacher J, Mikkelsen J, 2022) concurring with: while for men low relationship happiness, low compatibility in terms of sexual attitudes and values are principal factors in their engagement in marital infidelity, for women relationship factors are more important causative agencies than demographic variable like marital status and religious affiliation (Mark, Janssen, & Milhausen, 2011). Students who are securely attached, low in narcissism, and high in empathy are more likely to oppose sexual behaviors outside of their dating relationship even if their commitment level may be relatively

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low(Jessica Shimberg, 2016). To avert dissatisfaction in a marriage which could lead to extramarital affairs among other matrimonial problems, forgiveness, empathy and attachment proved to be of significant value(Febdi Hermawan, 2020).

Male dominance

In generally terms, for any partnership to register significant success with all members feeling proud of it, the decentralization of power and enforcement of critical rules and agreements is fundamental. Thus, by denying others reasonable participation in the decision making processes, they are not only being disadvantaged but made powerless and likely to be subjected to abuse in the future if necessary measures are not instituted(Tim Hamilton, 1996). In many societies including patriarchal ones, power dominance by the male counterparts have resulted to females being subjected to abuse including enduring and forceful normalizing of antisocial behaviors in which they are the principal victims such as extramarital affairs(Yandisa Sikweyiya, 2020): the desire to prove manhood, masculinity and women being under the control of men supported by societal beliefs and religious practices that a real man should not stay without extramarital sex/partner has significantly contributed to the prevalence of marital infidelity in some communities(Mtenga et al., 2018). The desire to prove manhood (masculinity) backed by some societal normative beliefs like, it is not normal for man to stay without extramarital partner and the religious belief that women should be dominated and controlled by men has significantly contributed to men engagement in extramarital sex(Mtenga et al., 2018). Males who have been engaged in extramarital relationship were higher in the social dominance even when compared to unfaithful females(Wróblewska-Skrzek, 2021).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the causes of extramarital relationship encompass cultural and traditional factors, strong desire for children, high level of education, loneliness, unattractive partner, lack of communication, poverty and financial hardships, lack of commitment to the marriage institution, dissatisfaction, access to the internet, lack of employment opportunities and working abroad, lack of personal boundaries, access to contraceptives, diseases and pandemics, substance abuse and drug addiction, domestic violence, lack of trust and respect, feeling unappreciated and care for, low level of education, normalization of infidelity, compulsive desire for sex, strong desire for revenge, stress at workplace, elevation in power, attachment style, childhood trauma, childhood exposure to infidelity, lack of moral standards and previous cheating, lack of religious commitment, low compatibility and empathy; and male dominance. However, these can be pooled and catalogued into social, cultural, economic and psychological factors.

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